

IDEAL PROFILE OF EDUCATOR FOR ADOLESCENTS WITHOUT A VALID FAMILY SUPPORT

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Abstract

In many countries the concept of educator has rather wide understanding and interpretation. Presented theoretic Christian issue reveals a profile, as far as possible close to the model of vocational counseling for adolescents without a valid family support. The needs that are common to this group of youngsters have, obviously, totally peculiar characteristics, and in this way could be described as special needs. To these special needs and necessities are added those deriving from the ways of management of living in a community, when this, for example, is based on the pedagogical methods of the so-called self-government.

Theory and practice applied in the community of Città dei Ragazzi presents educational action carried out by Msgr. J. P. Carroll-Abbing. The main issue of which is support, assistance and love for youngsters coming from different parts of the world.

Key words: *Christian paradigm of vocational counseling, role of educator, vocational counseling.*

Introduction

The youngsters who live in the Christian community of Città dei Ragazzi, has no valid family support: family is almost completely non existent, due to the death of one or both parents, for separation or divorce, for juridical problems, abandonment of the family, or for economic-social conditions such as poverty, being a refugee, social disadvantage. The institution actively exists in Italy since the Second World War.

High skilled, conscious educator with specialized knowledge, feeling a great passion for education is capable to meet a great number of needs of the youngsters who are in situation of insufficient support of their families. Educator who makes a difficult choice and individuates himself in this situation must be open to the general and individual needs of the teenager and community, to serve taking essential factors in developing youngster's personality, strengthen his inner sources for future life. In this aspect adequate and efficient vocational counseling is

one of his main personal capacities: *to educate* that particular boy that has been entrusted to him.

Comment on the term of Vocational Counseling

The verb to educate is extremely essential in its Latin etymology and gives a very bare profile and it is insufficient to understand the model of “*vocational counseling*” for youngsters with *special educational needs*. The sense of *e-ducere* = *conduct, bring out* is not enough to indicate the complex of educational operations, which, if it works, brings to the *liberation* from natural and inducted conditioning to development, to the growth and formation of the personality of the youngster. Even the concepts of *action* and *pedagogy* enrich the *educational operating* and bring more adequate definition of education in general, and of the educational relationship, in particular. These relationships which involve two people on the basis of reciprocal knowledge, exchanges of operative effectiveness, social experiences (often, competitive) contain all elements – active and passive – of the educational phenomenon, solid socialization and production of relational experiences.

In the recent years researchers (Marinelli, Dell Orto, 1999; Sharma, 2005; Stott, 2009; Merton, 2010) have individuated the word *formation* as more fitting to describe *education* rather than educational action: *formation* is the process through which the person constructs himself/herself, outlining his/her own identity; of formation as the action of building (Baranauskienė, Juodraitis, 2008, Baranauskienė, Radzevičienė, 2010), which evokes the concept of building and structuring of the personality.

In this way it could be pointed out that the word *formation* gets suitably close to a definition of *education* that mostly involves the educator and educated in the educational action.

For example, these words bring to mind one of the fundamental needs of the adolescent: the need of *self-government* that – according to the more advanced theory of science of education – creates an instrument of responsibility, of maturing, of participation, of development of the civic sense in the youngster; supported in the formative self-management, the adolescent aims at being self-sufficient, personal freedom, which should be identified with the same aim of education.

In this aspect the model of educator should be perceived as the ability to understand primary need of the boy, to share his personal worth, and to develop own professional competencies regarding the dynamics in educational methods in continuous development – to support, guide, to remind, when needed, act with energy forming positive behaviors (Vocational training handbook: a practical guide to planning and implementation of vocational training programmers with refugees in a developing country context, 1994, <http://www.nrc.no/engindex.htm>).

A special method of vocational counseling

To reveal the attitudes and the needs of self-government of adolescent, the educator besides of disposing of an adequate base of professional “know how”, should have more instruments to point out his value of cultural patrimony, to make his personality almost charismatic.

Towards authoritative position (not authoritarian!) to the youngster, the educator must be able to obtain understanding and agreement on ordinary and extraordinary actions, discipline in community and colleagues’ management, behave with operators who are near to him. The sensibility and the attention in the critical moments of the youngster’s life – being interested in his problems – give to the educator the key to his (youngster’s) heart, to his mind, enquiring how things are going on. The availability to be near to him, when things are not going well,

in helping him to discover his capabilities, encouraging him to believe in his possibilities, challenging him to using them, exactly in the moment when the youngster is convinced he is not good at anything (Baranauskienė, Juodraitis, 2008; Baranauskienė, Radzevičienė, Valaikiene, 2010), trusting him to take independent decisions, without fearing to make a mistake; and if he does it, trying to encourage him, without making a drama.

The list of situations of intervention of vocational counseling would be without end, because without end are the aspects of a life lived in operative symbiosis between educators and educated.

Everything can be summarized in a few paragraphs of commitment for an educator, professionally prepared, but mostly aware of his delicate mission and committed to carrying it out to the service of people who need him, personally! The “hello” that you did not give him this morning, will could never be heard from anybody! (Carroll-Abbing, 1965).

In synthesis: *educational presence* (to give the youngster the certainty that he is not alone); *dialogue, active listening and communication* (listening to him, speaking to him); *educational love* (being near to him, to serve him). These ideas are relevant today as well for those, who choose to dedicate themselves to helping youngsters with the particular need of recuperating, through education, the great values of guide of his own life.

At this point the definition of *vocational counseling* requests a more accurate name to express more clearly the specific differences of the general concept of the idiom. The general names of *educator, tutor, preceptor, pedagogue* must be substituted because each one of them only partially qualifies the concrete and efficient function, *παῖς* (the child) needs to grow.

The word *assistant* certainly is more appropriate. Even the Latin etymology is much more convincing: *ad-sto=I stand near to = I remain vigil and available to the needs of*.

Problem of the research: How is it possible to individuate the necessary attitudes for educator’s profession in Christian understanding of modern education?

Object of the research: Christian understanding of ideal profile of educator for adolescents without a valid family support in the aspect of social integration.

On the ground of the analyses from methodological point of view, **the research aims** have been drawn:

- 1) to conceptualize essential categories ensuring the success of vocational counselling for children and youth having SEN, based on the Christian understanding of modern education and social integration.
- 2) to reveal the content and forms of education as well as to present *the ideal* model of vocational counselling based on the experience of Città dei Ragazzi Community.

Methods and methodology of the research: Observation of scientific literature, analysis of heritage of Msgr. J. P. Carroll-Abbing were used to reveal main issues of Christian standpoints of social integration. Empiric data have been collected by using ethnographic research. This type of research was chosen because it reflects societal behaviour of people that enables to study the phenomenon and diversity of vocational counselling more deeply in different EU countries. Research data have been gained during the natural observation and complemented by the interview method, analysis of documents and assessment by expert groups. The data have been processed by logic analysis aiming to reveal completeness of the system of vocational counselling in Italy, on the base of the theoretical conception of the support mechanisms of the system of vocational counselling for pupils having SEN, while revealing the links of interaction of assessment criteria. Certain criteria of support mechanisms of the vocational counselling system for pupils with SEN (see Table 1; authors Baranauskienė, Juodraitis, 2008) were defined. It consists of 4 notional blocks that allows describing and understanding peculiarities of analyzed phenomenon.

Empiric data for the research have been collected using the method of structured discussion (free conversations with staff, students, and ex-students), method of observation (observing the communication between staff and students) and narrative method describing and revealing the essential features that let better understand the phenomenon of vocational counselling of SEN pupils.

Participants of the research: In the research 35 youngsters of Boys' Town from the 11 to 17 years of age have participated and 20 teachers and specialists working in the Boys' Town, as well.

Table 1. Support mechanisms of the vocational counselling system for pupils having SEN (Baranauskienė, Juodraitis, 2008)

Support mechanisms for socio-educational participation (individual and group)
1. Active participation of pupils having SEN
2. Competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation

Support mechanisms of the vocational counselling system for pupils having SEN were conditionally divided into two blocks: 1. Support mechanisms for socio-educational participation (individual and group) and 2. Socio-educational institutional support mechanisms.

The block of support mechanisms for socio-educational participation (individual and group) could be assessed learning more about:

a) *active participation of pupils having SEN* in the process of vocational counselling (acknowledgement of development of general abilities; understanding of the conception of consolidation of own value and constant perfection; (self-)development of motivation for working activities and societal life; acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development.

b) *competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation*, that could be understood by revealing changes of psycho-social environment; support in consolidation of pupil's personal value; support in choosing a profession; *accompanying support* during pre-vocational training; support in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling.

Assurance of reliability of data: Bearing in mind that the results of the ethnographic research often leave some doubts concerning reliability of data and validity of conclusions, in order to validate the research results the group of experts (counsellors) was formed; the group of three people got acquainted with the results not only of a particular research, but of the overall research as well. Remarks of experts and additional information provided by them will help in drawing final generalizations and conclusions.

Discussion on the results of the research

Support mechanisms for socio-educational participation.

1.a. Active participation of pupils having SEN

Acknowledgement of development of general abilities

The research results revealed that acknowledgement of development of general abilities of the boys who are out of their family has deep and well-organized traditions. From the first days of the attendance into the Boys' Town community boys are involved into the activities concerning everyday life problems and finding ways of effective solutions (see Table 2). During the first two weeks boys go under the observation of different specialists (educator, health specialists, psychologist, social worker, trainer of vocational skills) and they have possibility to get psychological (or any other) help if they are in need of it. Contemplation based on the Christian traditions plays a significant role in the acknowledgement of development of general

abilities. This activity is organized under the supervision of priests, other active members of Christian community that is actively involved into the education process of boys. It can be named as a model of “master-apprentice”. This model of assistance leads boys in all other activities of their life in Boys’ Town. It helps to estimate child’s disposition for particular activities in a very natural way. Generalizing information of observation, discussions, other obtained data, specialists make some suggestions for the child’s future vocational choice.

Table 2. Acknowledgement of development of general abilities

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Every day life activities	1. Activeness and volunteering in every day performance	1. Involvement in particular area of house keeping 2. Involvement in hobby activities	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker
Out-of-school school activities	1. Excursions to countryside, other places of interest 2. Attending in sport, art, technical activities	1. Interest in particular visits 2. Discussions with other boys/ adults on the topic of particular interest 3. Presentation of different kinds of creativity 4. Development of social skills and social activeness	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, tutors, social worker; representatives of Christian community
Lessons of general education	1. General subjects, technological education, physical education, lessons of music, fine art, an elective subject	1. Advanced marks in particular subjects of general education 2. Critical attitude towards own wishes and possibilities, general skills of living	Teachers; psychologist, special teacher of vocational counselling
Testing of students’ psychophysical characteristics	1. Setting some specific peculiarities associated with job activities	1. Appropriated decisions according to future vocational training	Educator-assistant; psychologist, special educator, vocation counsellor

Presented research data reveal the activities that are organized in Boys’ Town concerning development and recognition of general child’s abilities. Usually children test many of their practical abilities at home, while observing activities of parents. In the case of Boys’ Town pedagogues are assistants, parents and supervisors at the same time. Children can develop the main general abilities observing everyday life of the community that is close to the ordinary life style outside the community. Therefore, main sources for revelation of children’s abilities are observations of pedagogues that live together with boys in Boys’ Town.

Results of the research revealed activities of acknowledgement of general child’s abilities and certain indicators that can be defined. In the most cases acknowledgement of student’s abilities goes in all situations of child’s living in Boys’ Town period. It covers every day life and out-of-school activities. As usual, students are tested and assessed by institution psychologist, and results are discussed with specialists and the child as well. Testing is used as additional tool in recognizing child’s abilities and sustentation. Role of educator-assistant is significant in this situation and it continues the traditions of the Boys’ Town founder Msgr. J.P. Carroll-Abbing that stresses the special role of educator-assistant.

Understanding of the conception of consolidation of own value and constant perfection

It is important to understand the way in which person goes to personal perfection and the realization of the future. As boys placed in this institution have no adequate family support, their social experience sometimes is more negative than positive, extremely different social system of hosted country creates stressful situation not for boys only, but for caregivers as well. To realize own place in the new conditions and at the same time to draw the picture of the future requires the guidance of high-skilled professionals.

Research results reveal (see Table 3) that there are three main areas pointed as a measure to understand student's conception of consolidation of own value and constant perfection.

Table 3. Conception of consolidation of own value and constant perfection

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Reflection on self activities	1. Discussions with educator-assistant 2. Diary writing 3. Visits to the Boys' Town Chapel	1. Asking for free time for non-formal discussion 2. Collection of ideas of known people, discussions on personal problems in close environment 3. Visits to the Boys' Town priest and other members of Christian Community	Educator-assistant; peers, priest, nuns
Evaluation of one's achievements by others	1. Awards in Common events of Boys' Town 2. Discussions on successful topics with peers	1. Sense of pride being awarded 2. Active and prolonged debates with peers	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker; peers
Promotion of new ideas	1. Suggestions to Boys' Town community discussing significant questions 2. Election to the Executive Board of Boys' Town	1. Active participation in Community meetings 2. One of the elected positions in the Executive Board of Boys' Town	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, special pedagogue; representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys' Town community

It is a serious task to understand the processes of consolidation of own value and constant perfection. Mainly it takes a long time and activities in different levels and different directions. Taking in mind fast teenager's development in value system and self-identification it is obvious that the process needs a serious management. This area is mostly associated with person's psychological structure and hardly goes under the pedagogic input. This is proved in certain areas: reflection on self activities, evaluation of one's achievements by others and promotion of new ideas in the context of self-perfection. As it was set up, a significant role in the process of consolidation of own value and its constant perfection is played by people who are surrounding a teenager. The success or fail of this process depends on their personal values system, professional competencies and experience in the work with students who have no support from their families.

In this process the recognition and support from aside plays a role of person's affirmation. This is a way in which student gets self-confidence and understands his place in the acceptable and important for him environment. In other words it assures long lasting own person's consolidation value and its constant perfection.

(Self-) development of motivation for working activities and societal life

Motivation is a significant psychic phenomenon that determines person's successful or unsuccessful participation in the societal life because of its close connection with the characteristics of life quality and at the same time with the successful participations in the labour market. Taking into the mind the age of students who live in Boys' Town, there is a problem of self-development and the motivation concerning working activities and societal life in most cases is problematic. This has been proved by the analysis of research participants: 28 of all students have the experience of delinquent behaviour, all of them (70) have no sufficient support of families, in their childhood they have experienced neglect associated with poverty, war or ethnic conflicts. That is why self-identification in new situation, new communication and social experience has a significant role in the processes of self-identification and motivation that lead to success in societal life.

Community is the main area where (self-) development of motivation for working activities and societal life takes place. Together with the interest in societal life associated with gaining information on job (see Table 4), students perform a lot of practices that let them identify themselves in a particular sphere either in the relationship with adults, peers, or in the area of professional interest. Usually, all the staff of the community is involved in this process. Important place in it is taken by conversations with Christian representatives that work in the community, as well as other students living in the community area. This work helps students going from Boys' Town to reality that sometimes is not friendly and creative for young people. Strengthening beliefs, knowledge, realistic life attitudes and self-confidence, they are prepared for successful societal life and work.

Table 4. (Self-) development of motivation for working activities and societal life

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Additional training activities in lessons of general education	1. Staying in laboratory rooms after finishing of lessons 2. Asking for new knowledge and practice during the lessons	1. Close and informal relations with vocational training teacher 2. Interest in new equipments and materials for job activities	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, teachers of subjects in general education
Selection of particular information	1. Purposeful selection of materials concerning the area of interest 2. Looking for peers and adults who are at the same area of interest	1. Collection of materials concerning the area of interest 2. Friendly relationships and joint activities with peers, adults who are at the same area of interest	Educators-assistants, tutors, social workers, teachers of vocational counselling and training, peers
Volunteering in Community life	1. Help for the community staff in keeping order	1. Volunteer help for gardener, house keepers, kitchen workers, etc. 2. Involvement in the assistance for the younger children	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker

Continued Table 4

Participation in public events of Community	1. Evident attempts to lead celebrations and other events 2. Activeness in preparation works	1. Organization of social events 2. Learning of poems, songs, etc. for participation in the community events	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, educator-assistance; representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys' Town community
Interest in public life	1. Interest in art, sport, other kinds of activities outside Boys' Town 2. Participation in public events	1. Visits to particular public events outside Boys' Town 2. Participation in the activities of public institutions outside Boys' Town	Teachers; educator-assistant; representatives of Christian community

Analyzing the results it was revealed that every identified area could be recognized by two indicators. Assessing these results it is possible to say that (self-) development of motivation for working activities and societal life covers all activities and could be recognized in all activities of Boys' Town and conventionally could be divided in trends: first one is associated with relationship with persons that are in the nearest student's environment (close and informal relations with vocational training teacher, friendly relationships and joint activities with peers, adults who are at the same area of interest, volunteer help for gardener, house keepers, kitchen workers, etc., involvement in the assistance for the younger children) and another one is associated with work activities that are directly pointed to the gaining of the improvement of vocational experience (interest in new equipments and materials for job activities (collection of materials concerning the area of interest; organization of social events; learning of poems, songs, etc. for participation in the community events; visits to particular public events outside Boys' Town; participation in the activities of public institutions outside Boys' Town). A significant role of social partners that help to organize events, developing student's (self-) development of motivation for working activities and societal life has been mentioned.

Table 5. Acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Steady attendance in learning process	1. Stable participation in general education lessons 2. Additional training activities in vocational education	1. Fuss about missing lessons 2. Asking for additional tasks and jobs that are not compulsory in education process	Educator-assistant; vocational counselling and training teacher, social worker
Transfer of new skills	1. New and adjuvant things (objects) made by person 2. Improving of obtained new skills in every day activities	1. Creative behaviour in every day life skills 2. Spending more time then usual in certain area	Educator-assistant; social worker; vocational counselling and training teacher

Discussions	1. Participation in sittings with the representatives of Christian community 2. Participation in sittings with the members of Boy's Town community	1. Active participation in discussions 2. Sharing their previous life experience with others 3. Applying with personal questions to the person they trust	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, special pedagogue; representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys' Town community
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Acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development depends on many factors that surrounds a youngster. This area is closely connected with motivation, self-awareness and support coming from the nearest environment. Student's responsibility for one's own professional career forms on the basis of some, even low, social experience and motivation. It could be assessed as complex work or the whole, long term education action that never stops. In the concept of acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development 3 areas (see Table 5) were set up: steady attendance in learning process; transfer of new skills; discussions. Great attention is paid to the process of education: according to the Christian tradition education is the basic youngster's activity that leads to full-value life. Analyzing the research data it was set up that the main areas of activities associated with responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development were:

- a) in the general learning environment (stable participation in general education lessons, additional training activities in vocational education)
- b) in interaction with peers and staff who live in the community (participation in sittings with Boys' Town members and representatives of Christian community).
- c) in active and motivated participation in every day activities (new and adjuvant things (objects) made by person, improving of obtained new skills in every day activities).

In the process of acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development the role of specialists is important. As usually, educator-assistant plays the main role trying to create situations and tasks in which the sense of responsibility could be revealed. To cope with uncertainty, fears, to help youngsters to understand their real situation and to highlight future milestones nuns, priest (sometimes psychologist) are always ready to be near teenager.

Assessing the process of acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development it is possible to say, that in all performed actions the activity and motivation of the student plays the most important role. That is why the community staff tries to organize motivating style of life at the same time developing responsibility, self-awareness and assistance.

1.b. Competent and motivated support of specialists

The mission of Boys' Town is to bring up young generation according to the Christian tradition and Msgr. J. P. Carroll-Abbing pointed out the exceptional role of adult in it: the assistant as an integral educator, guarantees the giving of "educational love" and effective dedication in guidance of a youngster, in the constant and discrete respect of his personality, of his feelings, of his privacy, and staying at his side, opens the way to self-esteem and confidence in himself, giving him the hope of a new and possible life. "The great lesson of love, the secret of happiness is in love and the essence of love is in serving!" (J. P. Carroll-Abbing, 1965, p.

47). In this research sector theory and practice of this type of educational action, carried out in Città dei Ragazzi, reveals main characteristics of educator.

Second sector of research, revealing support mechanisms for socio-educational participation (individual and group) is competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation. In the research sector “Active participation of pupils having SEN” the role of competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation was mentioned in the aspect of student’s motivation and activeness. This part is dedicated to understand the role of specialists who work in Community with boys who have insufficient support of their families. The content of professional competences and support will be discussed (see Table 6) presenting data concerning revealing changes of psycho-social environment; support in consolidation of pupil’s personal value; support in choosing a profession; *accompanying support* during pre-vocational training and support in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling.

Table 6. Change of psycho-social environment

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Supplement of needed information	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Subscription of special informational materials 2. Visits to the exhibitions, job places, and practical placements of students 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of subscribed journals, usage of web-sites 2. Individual or group visits to exhibitions according to pupils’ area of interest 3. Freewill visits to the places of practice with other Boys’ Town students 	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker; vocational counselling and training teacher
Organization of creative environment.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Supplement of additional materials for practice works 2. Tooled places for out-of-school activities 3. Organization of exhibitions of pupils handcrafts and ware 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Additional materials used in the process of general education practice lessons 2. Opportunity to use free time in tooled classes for soft skills development 3. Participation in exhibitions organized for special occasions 	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker; vocational counselling and training teachers; representatives of Christian community
Publicizing of achievements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information lists of Boys’ Town 2. Presentation of students’ work in the institutions of social partners 3. Usage of pupils’ work in the designing of Boys’ Town environment 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Publications about student’s achievements 2. Participation in social events out-of-school 3. Works used for Boys Town’ decorations 	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, special pedagogue; vocational counselling and training teachers; representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys’ Town community

To organize effective and at the same friendly educational environment is a great challenge to any institution of education. Again talking about youngsters from different cultures, social experience and peculiarities of their development to consolidate all factors into the one harmonious theory and operating practice requires a lot of attempts, competences, professionalism and experience from the staff members. The competent support must be appreciable in all areas of child life and always. The results of the research show three areas of

changes in psycho-social environment that is directed to develop youngster's personality. They are: supplement of needed information, organization of creative environment, publicizing of achievements. These general areas were defined according to performed activities that reflect 2-3 ways of recognition. The youngsters mainly get competent support in the Boys Town' area. Presenting different professions the Boys' Town professionals try to assist, but not to be leaders. The assistance is mentioned in supplement of additional materials for practice works, organization of exhibitions of pupil' handcrafts and ware, presentation of students work in the institutions of social partners, usage of pupils work in the designing of the Boys' Town environment. Other activities that reflect educators' competence in the support of vocational guidelines are publicity, directed to strengthen students' self-confidence and motivation for his own choice (subscription of special informational materials, visits to the exhibitions, job places, and practical placements of students, information lists of Boys' Town, tooled places for out-of-school activities. In all these activities educator-assistant is near the student and at any time he is ready to help a child. It must be mentioned that staff working in the Boys' Town belongs to the actively operating Christian community and everyday Boys' Town routine and traditions are based on these issues.

Professional competences were revealed assessing support in consolidation of pupil's personal value as well. In the practice of Boys' Town it is an essential issue to take into mind specific contingent of students. According to the results of discussions with staff and with youngsters it is obvious that most of them before coming to the Boys' Town had extremely low self-value, often they experienced problems that are common to refugees. The changes in personal value might be affected by the child's coming to other culture, traditions, due to their experienced abuse and neglect in their birth countries.

Table 7. Support in consolidation of pupil's personal value

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Encouragement of practice activities with pupils	1. Planning of new handcrafts, ware that could be used in Boys' Town everyday life 2. Analyzing work process as possibility of self-realization	1. Meetings in the Boys Town Council Board planning Town's activities 2. Discussions with caregivers on the topics of person's values and growth in the context of Christian issues	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, special pedagogue; vocational counselling and training teachers; representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys' Town community
Planning of future activities	1. Discussions on planning exact future periods associated with job and learning activities 2 Consultations with consulters out of Boys' Town	1. Listing of exact activities dealing with realistic understanding of boy's future 2. Meetings with vocational consulters and visits to particular job and learning places	Educators-assistants, tutors, social workers, teachers of vocational counselling
Reflective practices	1. Meetings with ex-students of Boys' Town 2. Self evaluation in the context of own expectations	1. Participation in discussions with older students 2. Open and repeated conversations with educator-assistant	Educators-assistants, representatives of Christian community; boys living in the Boys' Town community

While analyzing the research data three main areas were recognized and identified as a process of competent support for consolidation of pupil's personal value (see Table 7). They are: encouragement of practice activities with a pupil, planning future activities, and reflective practices. Each area contains some indicators that reflect content and activities of support. Collected data (discussions, conversations with staff, students, and ex-students, observing staff's and student's communication) let draw some ideas about consolidation of student's self-value. All plans, strategies of institution, everyday problems and suspicions are discussed together with students when personal or group questions are needed to be solved. At the same time the operating activities are really socially actual for student and important for the Boys' Town community, as well. Educators and other specialists who are working in Boys' Town try to reveal the best features of student's personality and to present it to others.

The self-value of the student is consolidated in the planning of new handcrafts, ware that could be used in Boys' Town everyday life, meetings with ex-students of Boys' Town, consultations with consultants out of Boys' Town. Special attention is paid to the individualized work with students.

Supporting the consolidation of pupil's personal value closely associated with psychological characteristics, educator-assistant must have deep knowledge and experience to deal with teenager in a highly competent way, in order to develop full value personality. Individual work is performed in analyzing processes as possibility of self-realization, in discussions on planning exact future milestones associated with job and learning activities and self-evaluation in the context of own expectations. Generalizing issues of support in consolidation of pupil's personal value the exceptional role of educator who must be high-skilled in his activities must be outlined.

One more significant area of educator support is directly associated with vocational counselling. It is included in the whole understanding of institution's mission and basic Christian statements on person's value and the interaction with environment.

Discussing the research data on the support in choosing a profession five areas were revealed (see Table 8): presentation of professions that could be acquired in the basis of Boys' Town education; visits to the Boys' Town museum; meetings with representatives of different specialties in/and out-of-school; discussions among Boys' Town wards; giving any possible information concerning the profession of interest. The basis of vocational training in the Boys' Town is equipped with modern technology and specialists in vocational training could offer a lot of popular and marketable positions.

Table 8. Support in choosing a profession

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Presentation of professions that could be acquired in the basis of Boys' Town education	1. Lessons during general education process 2. Information on the student's request	1. Some particular questions or activities after lessons 2. Asking for additional or new information concerning presented professions	Educator-assistant; social worker; teachers of vocational counselling
Visits to the Boys' Town museum	1. Introduction of students' achievements in different professions	1. Active interest in the works and students whose handcrafts are in exhibition	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker

Meetings with representatives of different specialties in and out-of-school	1. Active participation in meetings with persons of different specialties 2. Interest in organizing meetings out-of-school in order to get information concerning certain professions	1. Participation in different kinds of meetings with Boys' Town guests 2. Asking educators to give opportunity to meet with adults in their work place out of school	Director, teachers, social pedagogue, special pedagogue; representatives of Christian community
Discussions among Boys' Town wards	1. Organized and free discussions at free time 2. Cognitive activities offered by boys to learn more about certain professions.	1. A group of boys who often meet to discuss about future work	Boys living in the Boys' Town community; teachers of vocational counselling
Giving any possible information concerning profession of interest	1. Free discussions with Boys' Town specialists 2. Information sharing with peers	1. Answers to the particular questions of boys 2. Pointed out sources of information, concerning professions (websites, checklists, and statements, etc.)	Educator-assistant; teachers; psychologist, special teacher of vocational counselling

It is valuable that students can develop their vocational skills in the Boys' Town, working with well known teachers and counsellors. Sector of vocational training has agreements with large enterprises, which are open to employ Boys' Town students. The mentioned situation is important talking about support in counselling process of young students who are Boys' Town newcomers. Even created environment could be assessed as supporting in the profession choice. The role of educator-assistant in this field is significant as well. Educator-assistant has a role of coordinator in every particular case. He together with a student decides content, links, and organizational measures in the support for the profession choice. Activities take place in the area of general education (lessons during general education process; active participation in meetings with persons of different specialties) and in the out-of-school time and place (information on the student's request; introduction of student's achievements in different professions; interest in organizing meetings out-of-school in order to get information concerning certain professions; organized and free discussions at free time, cognitive activities offered by boys to learn more about certain professions, free discussions with Boys' Town specialists, information sharing with peers). It is obvious that main activities take place out of lesson time and has non-formal character of education. It reflects the main mission and theoretical statements of Boys' Town, as a representative of Christian Community.

Other step in the competent and motivated support is accompanying process by specialists. It means that the support in student's activity gaining some information and work with information in the vocational counselling is concerned. In this sector individual and professional characteristics could be revealed. Process of accompanying support of educator assistant during vocational counselling is a dynamic activity that could hardly be planned exactly and must be flexible to respond to student's abilities and needs. It is a two-sided process created by educator-assistant and student.

Table 9. Accompanying support of educator assistant during vocational counselling

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Given information before planned activity	1. Preparation of learning materials for the students for lessons of technical and agricultural education	1. Active studies of given materials 2. Discussions on given materials after the general education lessons	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker; teacher of vocational counselling
Direct participation in joint discussions	1. Discussions in groups in the job places 2. Modelling possible activities associated with profession	1. Participation in discussions having appropriate level of knowledge 2. New ideas and suggestions that could be applied in training process	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, teacher of vocational counselling
Individual work with a student	1. Students' counselling according to individual needs 2. Provision of new materials that are in interest area of the student	1. Appealing to teacher of vocational counselling according to scheduled time 2. Beforehand prepared questions or topics for discussions	Educator-assistant; teacher of vocational counselling

Analyzing accompanying support of educator-assistant during vocational counselling three areas were pointed out: information before planned activity, direct participation in joint discussions and individual work with a student. The content of accompanying support depends on many factors such as student's developmental peculiarities, his experience and cultural traditions, his social and soft skills. Educator must know youngster's world well in order to assist with great sense.

During collecting observation data it was realized that even preparation material for support in vocational counselling is prepared taking into account students' cultural heritage, his level of knowledge. Usual they organize a lot of visits to the work places of their social partners and at the same time being, working and playing together turn to the accompanying support and assistance of vocational counselling (preparation of learning materials for the students for lessons of technical and agricultural education; discussions in groups in the job places).

The main role in the accompanying process is to show the attractive and interesting aspects of profession and to motivate students for choosing it. Mostly individual practices are organized by educators in accompanying support during vocational counselling. This could be acknowledged in modelling possible activities associated with profession; students counselling according to individual needs; provision of new materials that are in interest area of the student.

Generalizing results it could be pointed out that accompanying support of educator-assistant during vocational counselling is a dynamic and flexible process that corresponds to student's abilities and needs.

The last area of understanding of competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation is support in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling. It is final, very important and responsible step for the student's nearest future. It is a long term process and sometimes without answer. According to the vocation planning processes it seems to be in the ending of the counselling activities. Anyway, its continuity could vary depending on the various aspects and reasons. That is why exact edges in this process cannot be defined.

Table 10. Support in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling

Area	Acknowledgement	Indicators	Responsible persons
Testing of students abilities	1. Special tests used by institution's specialists 2. Conversation with psychologist and special educator	1. Data on the level of student's development 2. Specific suggestions on possible profession	Educator-assistant; social pedagogue, social worker
Discussions on appropriate professions and work value issues	1. Observation of professions that could be suitable for a student 2. Meetings and conversations with ex-students of Boys' Town	1. Meetings with Boys' Town professionals 2. Attendance in free discussion with ex-students of Boys' Town 3. Conversations with representatives of Christian community.	Educator -assistant; social pedagogue, social worker; representatives of Christian community; ex-students of Boys' Town
Special help in soft skills training	1. Planning and organizing of additional workshops and workshops for students in vocational training classes	1. Participation in soft skills training session 2. Improvement of performing soft skills activities	Teacher of vocational counselling; teacher of vocational training; educator-assistant

Analyzing support in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling first of all responsibility of educator must be mentioned. It looks like a youngster takes decision independently, by himself, but in fact the counselling must be done in such a way that student could choose the most appropriate professions for him. It requires high professional skills and competencies. Three main areas (see Table 10) were indicated assessing support (and the need of support) in solution of personal difficulties related to vocational counselling: testing of students abilities; discussions on appropriate professions and work value issues; special help in soft skills training.

Mostly all specialists take place in this process and everyone of them has direct responsibility area. They are performing such activities: special tests used by institution's specialists; conversation with psychologist and special educator; observation of professions that could be suitable for a student, meetings and conversations with ex-students of Boys' Town; planning and organizing of additional workshops and workshops for students in vocational training classes. The exceptional role in this area is shared with representatives of Christian Community. Their accompaniment during student's life in the Boys' Town has a great additional influence in the context of traditional educational methods. This aspect was mentioned by the staff during discussions with them.

Conclusions

Generalizing research results according to the areas of active participation of pupils having SEN and competent and motivated support of specialists – mediation, such conclusions could be drawn out:

1. Support mechanisms according to the active socio-educational participation of pupils having SEN (individual and group) could be an acknowledgement in evaluation of child's ability, discussions and participation in Boys' Town activities. Role of educator-assistant is significant in this situation it continues the traditions of the Boys Town founder Msgr. J. P. Carroll-Abbing that stress special role of educator-assistant.

2. Recognition and support from aside plays a role of person's affirmation. This is a way in which student gets self-confidence and understands his place in the acceptable and important for him environment. In other words, it assures long lasting person's own consolidation value and its constant perfection.
3. Participation in the activities of public institutions outside Boys' Town. A significant role of social partners that help to organize events, developing student's (self-) motivation for working activities and societal life has been mentioned.
4. Assessing process of acknowledgement of responsibility for own professional career and active participation in its development it can be said, that in all performed actions the activity and motivation of the student plays the most important role. That is why the community staff tries to organize motivating style of life at the same time developing responsibility, self awareness and assistance.
5. Professional competences were revealed assessing support in consolidation of pupil's personal value as well. According to the results of discussions with staff and with youngsters it is obvious that most of them before coming to the Boys' Town had extremely low self-value, often they experienced problems that are common to refugees. The changes in personal value might be affected by the child's coming to other culture, traditions, due to their experienced abuse and neglect in their birth countries.
6. The self-value of the student is consolidated in the planning of new handcrafts, ware that could be used in Boys' Town everyday life, meetings with ex-students of Boys' Town, consultations with consultants out of Boys' Town. Special attention is paid to the individualized work with students.
7. It is obvious that main activities take place out of lesson time and has non-formal character of education. It reflects the main mission and theoretical statements of Boys' Town, as a representative of Christian Community.
8. Their accompaniment during students' life in the Boy's Town has a great additional influence in the context of traditional educational methods. This aspect was mentioned by the staff during discussions with them.

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